

THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF BREAST MILK AND ITS
BIOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE.

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Annotation: *This article breast milk is an important nutrient for the baby. Contains breast milk the amount of components and their ratio is such that the system is intensive the demands of the growing child and its composition.*

Keywords: *milk, nutrient, baby, immune, blood, virus.*

Breast milk is an important nutrient for the baby. Contains breast milk the amount of components and their ratio is such that the system is intensive c1an fully meet the needs of a growing child. Natural the hormonal development of the fed child, as well as his organism unable to produce sufficient amounts of immune granules In the first months, it plays a key role in protecting the baby from infectious diseases. An artificial, mixed mixture of breastfed babies who are exclusively breastfed it is clear that it is 2.5 times less common in malnourished children and 25 times less common in patients with gastrointestinal diseases is proof. It is also new in the constant physical contact of the mother and childconstant protection in the newborn, a feeling of warmth, and motherly affection in the mother This means that in the future the child will be exposed to the social environment, and the mother will become pregnant facilitates the adaptation of the fetus to the postpartum period. Oral from the mother's breast for the first 3-4 days after birth milk, and from 6-7 days of adult breast milk. Milk also contains macrophages and neutrophils. Participate in this defense The progenitor cells also retain their physiological properties in the child's body and their participation in the process of phagocytosis of microbes Vitamin A and carotene in breast milk compared to mature milk amount 2-10, 2-3 times more ascorbic acid, including vitamin V12 and Eat 1.5 times more salt. Summary of the above evidence It is possible to breastfeed a newborn baby role in the process of adaptation to the external environment in the early days extremely large and this product is no other animal or artificial product cannot be replaced with. Protein, fat, carbohydrates in mature breast milk, The amount of minerals, vitamins is in optimal proportions. Mature breast milk is its own chemically different from other milks, i.e. animal milk does. The protein content of breast milk is 2.5 times that of cow's milk less, 1.5 times more carbohydrates and 3.5 times less salts. Carbonated milk from breast milk, from carbonated water from cow's milk differs not only in quantity but also in quality. Breast milk contains b- slower absorption of lactose in the small intestine than α -lactose for which it reaches the large intestine. This is the case maintaining the same osmolar pressure in all parts of the small intestine On the

other hand, it reaches the large intestine on the ground the intestine forms the saprophytic microflora and the pH of the intestine (pH = 5.0-5.8) is optimal. In the formation of intestinal microflora and breast milk replaces the poly and oligo amino acids that make up carbonated water large, namely beta-galactoside fructose. That is why this article referred to as the “bifidus factor” in breast milk because other poly and oligo aminosaccharide components (they are more than 14) do not have such a property. Another valuable quality of breast milk oil is that it contains The amount of phospholipids is excessive and tickles the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract unsaturated fatty acids (kapron, caprylic, coprion and others) is a lack of quantity. Cow's milk contains a lot of these fatty acids high (11.7%). The fat in breast milk is more easily broken down than the fat in cow's milk. It also differs in its properties, such as absorption and assimilation. It's in breast milk This is due to the fact that fatty acids have a short carbon chain, as well as the presence of the enzyme lipase in milk. Besides Essential fatty acids also have a positive effect on intestinal protein absorption These fatty acids in breast milk (unsaturated) indicate MNS braking process, and arachidonic acid in the formation of its activity has a special place Phosphatides in breast milk relative to the amount of phosphatides in cow's milk several times larger at all stages of the lactation process. This the biological significance of phosphatides is that they feed from the stomach to the intestines The mass is evacuated in one go, the fat is approximately high in the intestine provides intensive absorption. With the fat in breast milk, the baby's body fully meets its needs fat-soluble vitamins. So too at the same time a vitamin that is given to prevent rickets in children who are naturally fed Prophylactic doses of D (if the child's mother is at least 2 hours a week is not recommended. Under a mother's sunlight 200-300 units of international influence if the weekly duration is less than 2 hours vitamin D is recommended. The child's need for vitamin A until the age of 1-2 years It has been found that breast milk can satisfy a sufficient amount, especially in the first 4-6 In the months to come, only the mother's daily ration should be properly organized (Vitamin A: Adequate amounts of carotene-containing nutrients). If this If it is not possible to include nutrients in the mother's diet, give the mother pure vitamin A. may also be recommended (V. Newman, 1993) The amount of vitamin A you get with your daily products is 660 ER / day (World III for breastfeeding women in the country) to 1540 ER / day (rich countries for women) is recommended. For children, this figure is the lowest The limit (according to WHO / FAO) is set at 180 ER / day. But for the formation of sufficient reserves of vitamin A in the child's body 350 to 370 ER / day per day in the first year of life, 400 at the age of 2-3 years It is recommended to take ER / day. The first of the children of developing countries For 13-24 months, this figure is 140 ER / day or 160 ER carotene per day qdefined (V. Newman, 1993). The amount of minerals known from Table 1 above more in cow's milk. But the amount and quality of minerals in breast milk is a child. The organism fully meets the requirements of growth. Ratios between individual minerals optimal, ie high tendency to be absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract, and that is why they are easier to digest than the minerals in cow's milk is absorbed. For example, the ratio of Ca and R salts in breast milk is in the baby's blood plasma ratio of 2: 1 - 1.3: 1 in cow's milk. iron content. the amount of trace elements such as copper and zinc in cow's milk relatively more.

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